

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18936592

Narrating Ecohumanism: Impacts of Ecological Devastations on Niger Delta Dwellers in Chimeka Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*

Judith Erere Obanor¹ & Dr. Stephen Kekeghe²

Department of English and Literary Studies, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

¹[ladyjuddie6@gmail.com/](mailto:ladyjuddie6@gmail.com) ²stephenkekeghe@acu.delsu.edu

ABSTRACT

Over the years, the devastation of the Niger Delta region by the crude oil and gas explorers has attracted the attention of literary writers and scholars. This study examines representations of the Niger Delta challenges in Chimeka Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday* (2010), paying attention to the degradation of the physical environment and its negative effects on the humans and the non-human inhabitants of the region. The novel was selected through purposive sampling, given its relatable depiction of the Niger Delta region, a region which has been lamentably affected by oil exploration. The study adopts Lewis Mumford's Ecohumanism, an offshoot Ecocriticism, as its theoretical framework. This theory is appropriate for the research as it accounts for the impacts of environmental degradation on the human inhabitants as portrayed in the examined text. The analysis shows that the novel explores the destructive activities (oil drilling and oil transportation) of oil companies in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria and the effects of such activities (oil spill, leading to the deaths of animals and humans, anger portrayed by the indigenes, and others) on the indigenes. The novel reveals that the various activities of drilling crude oil come with a lot of environmental, physical, and psychological damage. This representation of the negative effects on the animals and the residents of those areas, as depicted in the novel, is what this research interrogates. This research comes with a peculiar significance as it examines, not just the physical degradation of the novel's environment, but also the security, economic, and psychological impacts on the characters. These areas have been understudied in ecocritical investigations. The features of the study reveal the scholarly gaps which will be filled, and they justify the investigation.

Keywords: Ecological Devastation, Niger Delta literature, Ecocriticism, Ecohumanism, Chimeka Garricks

INTRODUCTION

Ecological issues are portrayed in literary works, and this shows the intersection between literature and environmental science. The representation of ecological issues in literary works is aimed at sparking discussions on the need and steps to be taken for the protection of the environment. The environment comprises human and nonhuman entities. These entities are usually represented in the various genres of literature and are investigated in research works. Ecology can be seen as the study of the earth, and how various components of the earth interact with one another. This view is similar to that given by Molles (2002), when he asserts that ecology is the study of the relationships between organisms and the environment. This assertion gives attention to the idea of interdependence. This means that, for survival, these components (organisms and their environment) depend on one another. Humans, for instance, depend on most of the environmental components for food, medicine, shelter, and other benefits. When humans then cultivate their farms to grow crops, the crops depend on the watering, manuring and other

post planting operations, carried out by the humans for survival. These human activities authenticate Buell's (1995) declaration that human culture is hugely connected to the natural world, that the culture affects the natural world and the natural world affects the culture. By extension of this interdependence, most animals (herbivores) depend on the plants for food and when the animals defecate or die, their droppings and bodies function as manures for the growth of the plants. This is the concept of interdependence which ecology deals with. Among the animals too, food is sourced as the carnivores hunt or prey on other animals for food. Specifically, this interdependence from the perspective of food is called food web; and it is an organic relationship. These environmental realities are usually captured and examined in creative and investigative works.

The relationship between the components of the environment can also be inorganic. Inorganic components are without life. They are, however, very relevant to the survival of the organic components. Inorganic components include water, sand, rocks, air, weather, and others. Plants and animals, which are organic components of the environment, need these inorganic components to survive. It is why, from the perspective of inorganic relevance, Haeckel (1866) sees ecology as the total relations of an organism to its organic and inorganic environment. Haeckel's view undercores that the inorganic environment is as relevant to the organisms as the organic environment. From Haeckel's view, the organisms benefit hugely from these inorganic components. Judging by the relevance of this interdependence, it can be concluded that a mismanagement or humans' involvement in unhealthy activities in the environment affects the availability of these components.

Ecological devastation means the ruins, caused on the environment due to different activities— especially human or natural. These devastations can manifest in the forms of natural disasters such as earthquakes, floods, and storms. All living things, including humans, animals and plants, get a share of the devastation. Aside from natural disasters, human activities, as already mentioned, also birth environmental devastation. Wars, for instance, are very destructive occurrences as shooting, bombing, and other activities harm both living and nonliving entities. These realities are expressed by Bourque et. al. (2005) when they hold the view that environmental devastation is the degradation of the environment. According to them, this degradation is as a result of the depletion of biotic and abiotic resources of the environment. The view of Bourque et. al. emphasises the reduction of biotic and abiotic resources. This reduction is usually caused by different events which unfold in the environment, ranging from air pollution, water pollution, indiscriminate felling of trees (deforestation), and other activities which threaten the existence of the environment. These episodes of devastation, which have been conceptualised, have been represented in literary works. This representation establishes the intersection of literature and the environment. Buell (1995) argues that literature is utilized to create a bond between the reader and the environmental realities of his society. Philip's reference to Buell's view establishes the utilitarian relevance of literature: creative writers weave works to portray different events which unfold in the society. As episodes of devastation continue to unfurl in contemporary society, creative writers continue to weave works to capture these issues through invented literary elements.

Judging by the scholars' view, environmental devastation occurs when an activity or activities negatively affect biotic and abiotic resources, causing a reduction in their numbers and/or quality. The biotic resources are the components of the environment that have life (living things: humans, birds, fishes, trees). When the destructive activities, as mentioned earlier, take place, water organisms die, the forests get exposed, land organisms and other organisms die. This destructive event causes a reduction in the number and quality of the organisms, and this is what Bourque et. al see as environmental devastation. Bourque et. al's view also gives attention to the reduction of abiotic resources (both in quantity and quality). These resources are without life, and they authenticate the earlier views, provided about the nonliving components of the environment. Human activities or natural occurrences can dry up water bodies, thereby reducing the number of water bodies in that environment. The activities can also reduce the quality of the water as the water gets negatively transformed from pure to impure, thereby making it unhealthy for consumption and unsafe for external application. These are episodes of environmental devastation, captured in Bourque et. al's view. Brown et. al (1987) assert on the concept of environmental

devastation. According to them, environmental devastation is also an occurrence of degradation in living and nonliving things due to pollution, deforestation and other activities. Reduction is a dominant consideration in the views on environmental devastation/degradation. This establishes that a drop in the number and quality of environmental components is the main reflection of environmental devastation.

Ecohumanism, as an intellectual and cultural paradigm, arises from the intersection of ecological consciousness and humanistic values, seeking to harmonise the wellbeing of humanity with the preservation and flourishing of the natural environment. Its conceptual genealogy can be traced to the broader historical currents of humanism, which emerged during the European Renaissance as an anthropocentric framework centred on human reason, dignity, and agency (Kristeller, 1961). While early humanism was primarily preoccupied with human intellectual and moral development, its philosophical core contained latent tensions with the ecological realities of the world, largely because Renaissance humanism inherited a dualistic metaphysics in which human beings were posited as separate from, and superior to, the nonhuman world (Merchant, 1980). The gradual incorporation of ecological ethics into humanistic thought, culminating in the notion of Ecohumanism, represents both a philosophical reorientation and a corrective to this anthropocentric inheritance. This reorientation was accelerated by the environmental crises of the twentieth century, including industrial pollution, deforestation, and climate change, which challenged the sustainability of purely human-centred development models (White, 1967; Naess, 1973).

There are existing studies which have examined the depiction of ecological issues in literary works. As a rehabilitative and transformative art (Kekeghe, 2021), literature creates awareness of ecological health. The efforts of scholars to examine the depiction of the environment in literary works underscore the interdisciplinary relationship between literature and environmental sciences. This continuous exploration of environmental challenges, framed in literary works, foregrounds the cyclic nature of literary research: each research creates a platform for another. Ajibola and Okoli (2022) examine the depiction of environmental issues in Achebe's (1966) *A Man of the People*. In the study, the researchers examine the exploitation of natural resources and the commodification and oppression of women. The study, however, presents a scholarly gap as the investigation is limited to female characters while the current study involves both male and female characters.

Anwar et. al (2024) also emphasize the roles of women as custodians of ecological balance, steering attention to their spiritual and physical link with nature. While Anwar et. al's study offers transformative insights into ecological matters, it does not examine the involvement of male characters and the psychological effects of devastation on characters as this study will do. Gogoi (2014) and Okoye-Ugwu (2013) explore how Achebe's (1958) *Things Fall Apart* presents a harmonious relationship between the precolonial Igbo people and their environment prior to colonial incursion. Gogoi's and Okoye-Ugwu's studies, however, do not examine the ruinous effects of the activities of multinationals as these activities are not portrayed in the primary text. Similarly, Abraham and Abdulmalik (2015) X-ray how mythological narratives in the novel, *Things Fall Apart*, project the community's ecological values, highlighting their spiritual connection to nature. Abraham and Abdulmalik's study also is anchored on the precolonial and colonial Igbo society which was without the activities of multinational companies whose activities will be examined in this study. Kekeghe (2019) examines ecological commitments in the poetry of Christian Otobotekere. Fakemi (2022) investigates ecological issues in Chimeka Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*, but it does not sufficiently reflect the negative effects of environmental devastation on characters. Fakemi's focus is chiefly on the disruption of the liberating efforts of some characters due to greed. Fakemi's study also does not examine the socioeconomic effects of environmental devastations. This is a scholarly gap, and this study will fill it.

From the studies reviewed above, it is evident that literary studies on ecological devastations in Nigeria have not adequately examined the effects of such ravages on the social, economic and psychological make-ups of the indigenes. This study, therefore, offers much significance as it interrogates these understudied areas of ecocritical investigations. This further justifies the study.

Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday* was purposively selected due to its sufficient depiction of episodes of environmental devastation. This research is a qualitative analysis of the representation of the effects of ecological devastation on the Niger Delta people as creatively depicted in the primary text. It is non-numerical. Literary analyses, like the current study, are usually qualitative as they are usually anchored on creative texts, their imagery, and how events reflect life's realities. The novel for analysis is rich in the depiction of environmental issues and other observable, literary features, hence the effortless decision to choose it for this qualitative, analytical exercises.

Although, there are existing studies on ecological issues, portrayed in literary works, the area has not been fully explored as there are still gaps which can be filled through interrogative extensions. This is a research problem. This research will pay attention to the socioeconomic, physical, and psychological effects of environmental devastation which the reviewed works do not examine.

This study examines the effects of environmental devastation on characters in the primary text. The specific objectives are to examine the portrayals of deaths, resulting from a polluted (devasted) environment. It will also analyze the depiction of the various effects of devastation. Identification of narrative devices will also be done in the course of the analyses.

This study will be relevant to the society at large. Environmental devastation is a contemporary issue, and it is experienced in different regions of the world as experienced in Africa. With the issues, which will be highlighted and examined in the study, awareness will be created for the different societies, plagued by this challenge. It will also help the societies make redemptive efforts to salvage situations of environmental devastation. In the academic field, departments in environmental sciences can benefit from this research as it will present, to them, a literary perspective of their field. Researchers will also benefit from this study as it will inspire further interrogations of texts through the revelation of a scholarly gap. The text which is analyzed, is Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*. In the novel, there are portrayals of environmental devastation and its effect on characters. The events are in line with the objectives of the the research, hence the decision to choose it (the novel).

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Lewis Mumford's Ecohumanism, an offshoot of Ecocriticism, as its theoretical framework. The theory expresses the connection between the ecology and humans, and it expands the ideas of Ecocriticism. Ecocriticism gained widespread attention in the 19th century, and that was after the publication of the text, *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology* by Glotfelty and Fromm in 1997. The scholars in the text expose readers to the tenets of ecocriticism as they state that it is the study of the relationship between literature and the environment. By this view, the researchers posit that a critic, who chooses ecocriticism for an analytical exercise, examines how man's environment is represented in the primary text(s). Since ecocriticism is anchored on environmental portrayals in primary texts, it is seen as earth-centred. Barry (2009) states that for the ecocritic, nature exists, that he, the critic, examines works of literature with the consciousness that humans affect the environment; and the environment in turn affects humans. Barry's view further substantiates the idea that ecology deals with the interaction among the constituents of the environment (interdependence). Rueckert (1978) was the first literary researcher to use ecocriticism. In his work, he states that ecocriticism is the application of ecology and ecological principles to the scholarly study of literary works. Rueckert's view implies that an ecocritic must possess in-depth knowledge of ecology (the environment). He, the ecocritic, then applies the knowledge to the close reading of the selected, primary text(s). His knowledge of ecology functions as the literary lens through which he locates the depiction of ecological challenges for an analysis. The major proponents of ecocriticism are Emerson, Fuller, and Thoreau.

Ecohumanism is an interdisciplinary, philosophical and literary theory which is deployed by humanist and environmental critics to interrogate the interconnectedness between humanity and the natural environment, discouraging selective prominence or a consideration of disparity between humans and the natural environment. This means that the theory advocates for a worldview where humans are not superior to nature but are part of a holistic ecological system. A researcher, who adopts Ecohumanism for an analytical reading of a creative text, deters the glorification of anthropocentric humanism --- another

aspect of Ecocriticism which centres human beings as the ultimate measure of all things. Ecohumanism, instead, insists that ethical responsibility must extend beyond the human to include non-human life, natural forces, and ecosystems. In other words, Ecohumanism emphasizes a harmonious and reciprocal relationship between humans and their environment, recognizing that ecological devastation is also a moral and existential crisis. The propounding of Ecohumanism is both an environmental ethic and a humanistic call to rethink the relationship between humans and their natural environment and how the sustenance of one is dependent on the other. Another renowned voice in Ecohumanism is Michael Eze. Eze's (2017) work is a demonstration of Afrocentric sentiment as it steers attention to the African perspective of Ecohumanism, arguing for a culturally grounded understanding of environmental responsibility, rooted in African cosmology and communal life. Eze emphasizes that the African thought naturally envisions spiritual and ethical entanglement between humans and the environment, rejecting both Western anthropocentrism and certain strains of ecological reductionism.

Eze's contribution to Ecohumanism prescribes the detection and repudiation of Western, environmental predilections in African literary works. Slaymaker (2001) corroborates Eze's philosophical choice as he, Slaymaker, discusses "eco-hesitation" in his work. The researcher deploys "eco-hesitation" to mean African intellectual reluctance to embrace Western-derived ecocriticism. Slaymaker calls for an eco-humanist model which intersects environmentalism with African sociocultural realities, especially those, tied to postcolonial identity and survival. Pursuant to this, the interrogation of human activities (ruinous or beneficial) and their effects on the environment, as framed in literary works, is the tenet of Ecohumanism. Many critics have deployed Ecohumanism in the interrogation of human activities and their far-reaching effects on the environment. Egya (2016) adopts Ecohumanism in the close reading of selected African poems which recreate engaging, environmental realities. In the study, Egya exposes the insidious activities of dwellers in the Niger Delta region as archetypally depicted in the poems. In the primary text for this study, there are conspicuous depictions of environmental devastations, engendered by the activities of the characters. These portrayals of degradation, resulting from the roles of these characters, justify the adoption of Ecohumanism as the theory for this investigation.

The contributions, examined in this section of the study, have revealed the tenets (principles) of ecocriticism. The views of the researchers have underlined that an ecocritical analysis examines environmental devastations (basically) and/or environmental improvement, depicted in a work of art. Environmental devastation is creatively represented in the primary text for this study, and this makes ecocriticism an appropriate theory for this exercise.

Depiction of Episodes of Human Carnage, Resulting from Environmental Devastation

In Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*, the devastation of the environment leads to the death of characters. The title of the novel, *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*, is paradoxical as it depicts a "tomorrow" which died before it appeared. This is a painful reality as it reflects the damage which will be noticed in the future due to past, human activities.

Tubo, one of the indigenes of Asiamia, works for Imperial Oil, an oil company that exploits the oil in Asiamia. He is sad about the kidnapping and the eventual death of Mr Manny, an expatriate who also worked for the company. Mr Manny is kidnapped, and he dies before his release. The kidnapping is carried out by Doughboy, an indigene and the leader of the Asiamia Freedom Army. Doughboy goes into kidnapping due to the exploitation of the environment and the neglect of the people's needs. As Tubo and the other workers in the oil company express grief over Mr Manny's death, Amaiba, one of the indigenes and a lecturer, questions Tubo's preference to mourn the death of a foreigner while ignoring the scores of dead indigenes who lost their lives (years ago) and those who have recently lost their lives due to the devastation of the environment. Amaibi confronts Tubo to express disappointment as he, Amaibi, says:

Tubo, your concern for the life of one oyibo is touching. What about the people [of Asiamia] who died in 1997? What about the lives of the Asiamia people who are dying prematurely because of Imperial's flaring? (p. 13).

Here, Amaibi conveys his dissatisfaction over Tubo's lack of concern for his dying people despite the worsening of their plight. Again, we see how Amaibi indicts Imperial Oil for the death of Asiamia people

due to the dangerous activities of the company. The activities of the oil company have clearly affected the people of Asiamia as reflected in the indigenes' deaths which Amaibi reminds Tubo of. Garricks uses this above conversation to mirror the episodes of carnage which used to characterise the Niger Delta region in the era of reckless exploitation of the oil in the various environments. The 1997 event in the novel, in which the indigenes of Asiamia were killed, is an allusion to different genocidal attacks on the Niger Delta people over oil drilling disagreements. An unforgettable one is the Odi massacre of 1999 in which over nine hundred civilians in the region were killed. Garricks clearly uses the similarities of these events to decry the insecurity, caused in the Niger Delta by oil-related disputes. These events again justify the appropriateness of ecocriticism as the theory for the analysis of this text as the events, analyzed already, reflect the principles of the theory. As conceptualised, ecocriticism examines episodes of environmental degradation, in a literary text, and their effects on the human and nonhuman environment.

The devastation of the environment contributes to the deaths of characters in the novel. It is expected that, after the pollution of the rivers which kills the fishes and renders residents hungry and unemployed, the characters will look for other means of survival as their responsibilities have not changed even though the ecology has changed. After Doye and Soboye's father has been rendered unemployed, Soboye goes into bunkering for financial revival. There is an explosion, and Doye's father is worried. He says he hopes Soboye was not involved in the explosion. The following excerpt reveals how they (Doye and his father) board a boat to the site of the explosion to discover that Soboye has been killed in it:

Papa stole a boat with an outboard engine... I could never imagine what we saw past there. A roaring fire, about ten feet high, marked the tiny uninhabited island where Soboye and twelve other people had gone to steal, or rather, bunker oil. The fire, bright and brilliant, gave enough light for us to see their deep-roasted corpses which littered the shore... Death from the pipeline explosion... We smelled the heady aroma of burnt flesh (p. 75).

In the excerpt above, the narrator reveals how Soboye was charred in an oil explosion. The adjectives "deep-roasted" and "burnt", which the narrator uses in the cited excerpt, show that Soboye was burnt almost beyond recognition. The narrator states that the smell was strong to reveal that the corpses were deeply burnt. The burnt indigenes are victims of ecological devastation. They die because they made illegal attempts to stay alive in a devastated environment. These events reveal Garricks' intention. He clearly projects, through the plot direction, that it is important to realise or consider the factors which inform the extreme decisions of the residents of the Niger Delta region. He also uses the event to remind readers of the different narratives of explosion in the Niger Delta due to bunkering and other illegal oil activities.

Asiamia people decide to riot against the devastation of their environment by Imperial Oil. They take the riot to the flow station, beat the workers, and shut down the flow station. The leaders of the company run to Chief Ikaki for help. He accepts to talk to the Governor to deploy soldiers to the flow station to reclaim it. Soldiers are eventually deployed to the area, and they demonstrate their characteristic show of unprofessionalism, brutalising and killing people in the process. In the excerpt below, Kaniye narrates how the soldiers kill Mpaka, Doye's father:

He [Mpaka] did not open his eyes when they shot him. The bullets pierced his body. He jerked a macabre dance as he welcomed them... He did not fall. The bullets could not silence Mpaka... Another short burst of gunfire... But still, he refused to fall. The final round of gunshots were angrier. It disintegrated half of Mpaka's face and slammed him on the ground... Everyone was fixated on the bloodied bloody. We waited for Mpaka to die (p. 231).

The gory scene, which the narrator paints above, stirs a deep feeling of pity for Mpaka who indirectly pays, with his life, for the devastation of his environment. The capturing of the flow station was what influenced the deployment of the soldiers who shoot Mpaka. The connection here is that the environment is devastated, and the affected characters convey their rage by capturing the flow station. This leads to a reaction from soldiers, and Mpaka gets affected as he loses his life. Environmental devastation is the root cause of this death and others. Mpaka dies because a flow station was seized in reaction to a devastated

environment. To describe the gruesomeness of Mpaka's death, the narrator deploys figurative language as he depicts the guns as being "angry" when he says that the final round of gunshots was "angrier". With this personification, the narrator, perhaps, tries to reveal that shooting increased in order to ensure that Mpaka's resilience was subdued. It is the painful reality of heinous killings in the Niger Delta region that Garricks depicts in the excerpt. On many occasions, in the past, the military reacted rashly to security issues in the Niger Delta region and on those occasions, many innocent people were killed.

Kaniye, the lawyer, gets a call from Mr Wali to go to a mortuary and identify a corpse. He, Kaniye, is confused as he wonders whose corpse it is. He proceeds to the mortuary. The excerpt below reveals a hugely damaged body:

The body was lying on the ground outside the Mortuary. A small, gawking crowd had formed a rough circle round the body... I walked up to the body. It was a man, a tall, muscular, well-proportioned man. He was naked,... Death had been violent. Dozens of bullets had riddled the body, leaving tiny, ugly holes, which flies excitedly buzzed over. The bullets had also shattered most of his face, except for his mouth. But I knew exactly whom it was (p. 248).

It is Doye's corpse. He has been killed by security operatives. It is revealed, through a series of flashbacks that Doye grew up a harmless boy. He grew up with some of the characters who do not join him in militancy. His decision to engage in kidnapping and killings was influenced by the devastation of the environment which revealed to him that his future would "die" if he did not engage in unlawful acts for survival. There were no clear plans by the oil companies to cushion the depressive effects of the environmental degradation of Asiamama. That compelled him, Doye, to get involved in unlawful practices; and they lead to his death. Doye's story rehashes memories of John Togo, an ex-militant leader in the Niger Delta. The dreaded John Togo was guilty of killing, kidnapping, robbery, and the abuse of human rights. When one examines Doye's roles in the novel, he sees a clear representation of John Togo who was the founder and leader of the Niger-Delta Liberation Force. Togo, like Doye, claimed he was fighting for the liberation of the Niger Delta from exploitation. The devastation of the Niger Delta, he claimed, informed his decision to go into militancy. He was killed by the Joint Task Force after many years of searching for him. Like Doye in the primary text, Togo was a terror to residents and expatriates. Through this allusive representation, Garricks further refreshes the thought about the issues of insecurity and militancy in the Niger Delta.

Representation of Death in the Nonhuman Environment of the Novel

The nonhuman environment is also affected by the activities of Imperial Oil. This foregrounds the far-reaching effects of environmental degradation. In the novel, Doye remembers how his father lost interest in fishing due to the oil spills and other forms of pollution which have continued to cause a drop in the quality and quantity of fish in the various rivers in Asiamama. His father is gradually drifting into unemployment as his major source of livelihood, fishing, has been devastated by Imperial Oil. In the excerpt below, Doye reveals the drop in his father's interest in fishing, the extent of contamination done on the water, and the devastating effect on the fish:

These days, Papa did little fishing. His reason was that Imperial Oil chased away most of the fish when it laid pipelines in the river and the ocean... This year there was also something that happened up on the Asiamama River. We woke up one morning to see oil, thick and black, floating on top of the brown water of the river. The river became sluggish in its flow, as the oil gradually choked its life away... fish turned on their sides (p. 73).

The description, given above by the narrator, is saddening. Doye's father no longer sees the need to go to fish since the number of fish has reduced due to oil spills. In the excerpt, provided above, Doye reveals the agonising event in which the water was polluted by oil spills from Imperial Oil and by consequence the death of fish. He uses figurative expressions to reveal the level of devastation which took place as he describes the pitiable state of the water. The figurative expressions are noticed as he views the river as a human that was suffocated to death as he says that the oil "choked" (p. 73) the "life" (p. 73) of the river

"away" (p. 73). Through this figurative depiction, the narrator rates the river, before the pollution, as being full of quality and relevant to humanity. The pollution/degradation therefore appears like death to him. This use of figurative expressions comes from a place of frustration. He also narrates the sad condition of the fish as he says they "turned on their sides" in death. The implication of this is that the residents will become unemployed, hungry and also endangered as they may use the polluted water. That will negatively affect their health.

Tubo receives an emergency call from his company. He runs and tells Amaibi that he needs to rush to his employers. Before he leaves, he reveals what the emergency is, as he tells Amaibi, "An oil spill just occurred in the Asiam River... From one of the Imperial pipelines" (p. 218). Kaniye Rufus, a lawyer, files a lawsuit on behalf of the Asiam Fishermen Cooperative in reaction to the oil spill, caused by Imperial Oil. Clearly, the lawyer, who is an indigene, does this because he is aware that the pollution of the river, which will result in the death of fish, will have devastating, economic and psychological effects on the people. In the following passages, the filing of the suit and how the spill killed the fish are revealed:

...The lawsuit was filed that morning, on behalf of the Asiam Fishermen Cooperative... It was filed by Kaniye Rufus. Attached to the court papers was a copy of a report detailing the ecological devastation caused by the oil spill...

The most damning things were the pictures: pictures of black oil gushing into the lifeless river, dead fish, damaged nets and traps, and the haunted faces of some fishermen (pp. 220-221).

We see how the episode of death, caused by water pollution, is presented again in the extract above. The activities of Imperial Oil have devastated the environment through the pollution of the river, resulting in the death of fishes and the destruction of traps. The narrator uses the colour "black" (p. 221) to appeal to the thought of the reader and to reveal the extent of the water pollution. He uses the phrase "lifeless river" (p. 221) to imply that the river has been degraded.

The Effects of Ecological Devastation on the Psyches of the Characters

In Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*, there is the portrayal of characters' psychological and emotional responses to the devastating activities of Imperial Oil. The oil company regularly drills the oil in Asiam Community with its gas flares, causing the deaths of indigenes. The activities also cause oil spills which pollute the rivers, making them harmful for use. The pollution, as well, results in the death of the fishes. As a riverine community, the indigenes are predominantly fish farmers. The implication of the oil spills is that the indigenes have been rendered unemployed, and they will be plunged into lack, and this poses severe negative impact on their minds.

Doughboy, who is the leader of the Asiam Freedom Army, intercepts a boat with an expatriate and security officers on board. His words reveal anger, a feeling of abandonment, and a feeling of exploitation. The mopol and the naval officer, whom he threatens, are from Kano and Ekiti States respectively. As an angry victim of a devastated environment, Doughboy expresses his feeling about the exploitation of Asiam in the fragment below:

"Hausa man." I lowered my voice. I didn't want my anger to show... "How can you, a Hausa man, be my brother? When you people were stealing our oil money all these years, was I your brother then?"... I turned to another one who was face down on the floor. He was in the navy uniform. I kicked him hard on his ribs.

"Hey, you! Where are you from?"

"Eh... eh... Ekiti State, sir." He kept his face down. He didn't want to look at me. I squatted near him. I whispered, "Yoruba man, are you my brother? He didn't know what to say..."

"My people have the oil, yet it is your people who have all the jobs in the oil company. You people refuse to employ my people. They say we are not qualified. Yoruba man, answer me—are my people not qualified?" (pp. 3-4).

The quotation reveals Doughboy's feeling of marginalisation in a devastated environment. We feel his anger as we see him prefer to speak along ethnic divides. He sees the security officers as representatives of the exploiters from the different regions of the country, hence he also unleashes his anger on them. The narrator reveals that Doughboy kicks the naval officer on his ribs. This act of violence uncovers his psychological state as an angry individual, living in a devastated environment. By connection, the devastated environment has triggered a psychological devastation leading to this portrayal of anger and violence. From an ecocritical angle, we see the effect of a devastated environment on the psychological status of the residents. Doughboy is devastated that non-indigenes come to his community to plunder the natural resources and become rich while the indigenes, the owners of the resources, remain poor. This is Doughboy's anger, and this influenced his decision to go into militancy to stay relevant economically and also to advocate an end to the exploitation of his community. His anger is also noticed in the following clip of the novel in which Tubo, the narrator, reveals the regular kidnapping which Doughboy has carried out and how he has regularly asked Imperial Oil to leave the Niger Delta:

In the past three years, Doughboy has been credited with eleven kidnapping involving eighteen Imperial Oil expatriate staff. The most recent was in January when he snatched Tanowitz, Morris and Bryson. As usual, Doughboy made a list of demands including the obligatory call for all oil companies especially Imperial Oil, to leave the Niger Delta, and Asiamia in particular (p. 6).

When Mr Mustapha, one of the leaders of Imperial Oil, asks that the attention of local authorities should be drawn to the scary happenings of kidnapping so they can find the kidnappers, Tubo says the local authorities cannot "even find their asses in a toilet" (p. 6). The sarcasm, which Tubo deploys during the conversation, shows how strong Doughboy and his men have become. Other characters now feel they, Doughboy and his men, are almost indomitable. These events of discomfort are engendered by Doughboy's decision to go into kidnapping due to anger over his devastated environment. Because of his involvement in kidnapping and other portrayals of brutality, Tubo thinks he, Doughboy, is psychologically devastated. In his conversation with Amaibi, Tubo tells Amaibi, "You know Doye [Doughboy] is a mad man and his boys are even crazier" (p. 12). He thinks that Doughboy's extreme reaction, to his devastated environment, is a demonstration of madness.

It is an irony that the characters, who live in Asiamia, a community rich in oil, do not have substantial sources of livelihood aside from fishing and farming which come naturally. It is more ironic to realise that non-indigenes are being enriched in the same community through the exploitation of the oil. Some, like Doughboy and his men, have reacted violently. There are others who have chosen a different path—prostitution, drug abuse and so on. Most of the young ladies in the narrative are without jobs. They cannot even resort to farming because the land has been degraded. They cannot go into fishing because the oil spill has polluted the rivers and has killed the fish in them. The characters are devastated, and some of them do not see options aside from prostitution and other condemnable practices. The excerpt below reveals Zion Hotel where educated female characters function as prostitutes in reaction to limited options, caused by a devastated environment:

Despite the somewhat grandiose name, the Zion was a low, U-shaped bungalow... Every night, the Zion boasted the single largest gathering of available women in Asiamia. Many were beautiful, young, even educated to some level, but they were all prostitutes. Years ago, their biggest clients used to be the company boys who were the expatriates... That was until the arrival of the oil boys, people like us: bunkerers, militants and politicians (p. 171).

It is agonising for the female characters when they realise they are educated but still not economically relevant. Providing legal jobs in Asiamia would not have transformed it into a perfect society, but it would have reduced the engagement in condemnable vocations. The educated female characters resort to prostitution in Zion Hotel in reaction to a devastated environment. The extract reveals that the prostitutes' biggest clients used to be the company boys, and that the company boys are the expatriates. The adjective

"big" underscores that the expatriates are living in wealth while the indigenes, the owners of the oil, live in lack and hopelessness. The female characters, perhaps, feel that they need to choose a vocation which will give them access to the money, amassed through the devastation of their land. Prostitution becomes the channel. Obviously, the devastated environment has influenced the female characters' choice of an illicit job since a dignifying one is beyond reach. The oil boys refer to the Asiamas who chose kidnapping and bunkering after nothing good came to them from a devastated environment. It is obvious that, initially, the boys could not afford the services of the prostitutes in Zion Hotel but can now do so because they have made money through illegal means. Their financial rise seems to make them justify their involvement in these illicit jobs. The oil boys, clearly, have become richer than the company boys. This is a financial status they would not have attained if they had remained passive about the devastation of their environment. The oil company's selfishness seems to have made Asiamas a breeding ground for unlawful practices.

Some of the characters go into oil theft. As stated already, the devastation of the environment has created illegal job opportunities for the disillusioned characters. Those, who are not able to cope with the devastation, resort to illegal activities which endanger their lives. As established in the theoretical framework, ecocriticism gives critical attention to how humans affect the environment, like the activities of Imperial Oil, and how the environment affects humans, as seen in the physical and psychological reactions of the characters to their devastated environment. Soboye and Doye (Doughboy) are brothers. Soboye has yielded to the thought of quickly finding a solution to his financial situation in a community which has been drilled for oil and ecologically destroyed. He chooses oil theft. In a conversation with Doye, Soboye talks about oil theft to indicate his interest:

There is an underground pipeline, a very long pipeline. It carries crude oil from Port Harcourt to Bobby for export. The pipeline passes through a thin swamp island, just after Juju Island, up the Asiamas River... Every night, some people go up the river to that swamp island. I don't know how they do it, but they load the oil in boats, come back down the river and sail into the ocean. There are ships already waiting on the ocean to buy the oil (p. 68).

The extract exposes episodes of oil theft in the Niger Delta region. The narrator reveals how Asiamas's crude oil is transported via a pipe to eventual buyers. The indigenes must have thought it wise not to be passive as non-indigenes enrich themselves. It is why Soboye reveals how some other characters in the narrative decided to steal some quantity of the oil for themselves. We cannot say that if there was no plundering of Asiamas's oil that no one would have gone into oil theft. However, it is certain that some or most of the characters would not have considered oil theft if they had been integrated into the oil sector or other sectors of the economy. The characters have decided to choose a career in oil theft as they cannot locate hope in their devastated environment. The realities, which Garricks recreates here, are very relatable. Experiences are very potent determiners of the volitions, made by individuals. Most individuals make decisions according to situations. The characters in the work have made decisions in accordance with their experiences, and this is reflective of relatable, true life experiences.

Consequences of Revolt Against Environmental Exploitation

Characters, who decide to revolt openly against the degradation of their environment, are intimidated, especially when they refuse to accept bribe to keep mute. They are intimidated by the profiteers in the state government and community government. It is a double loss for the indigenes as they lose their environment and also lose their fundamental human rights. It is an atmosphere of repression for them. Amaibi, a university lecturer, upholds his integrity in a devastated environment where power, influence and affluence are in the hands of few individuals. He regularly uses his intellectual status to expose the ills of Imperial Oil and most of the leaders in Asiamas. As a result of his integrity, he becomes a target of the government. Amaibi's revolutionary efforts earn him the attention of some aggressive security officers. They invade his house, shoot his leg, and throw him into prison. They accuse him of conniving with Doughboy in the various kidnapping incidents. He experiences this repression because he seeks an end to the devastation of his environment. The excerpt below shows his ordeal in prison:

I crawled quietly, feeling my way in darkness, towards the smell. I was lucky to find some unoccupied space near a wall. I sat upright and rested my bare back on the wall. It was cold. I shivered slightly, pulled my legs towards my chest, and wrapped my arms round my body. The smell of faeces was very strong now. I knew the bucket was about two feet away from me. I knew that big fat maggots were crawling happily on the wet floor near me (p. 32).

Amaibi is subjected to extreme torture in prison. The dehumanising nature of Nigerian prisons is depicted as the dirty environment brings discomfort to Amaibi. Aside from battling with the stench of the prison, he also has the agonising pain, triggered by the bullet wound, to battle with. He has chosen Kaniye, a caterer and lawyer, to handle his case in court. Different narratives are propagated to indict Amaibi. Kaniye visits him in prison, and he, Amaibi, stories in detail how he was captured:

You know how enthusiastic they [the mopols] can be about killing an ant with a sledge hammer. They came to my house very early one morning, almost a squadron of them. They smashed down my door command-style. They arrested me... in bed. I didn't resist. They beat me up. I didn't resist. Then, they shot me. I still don't know why. For months, I was interrogated and tortured by the police and the state security people, in Abuja, Kaduna and Maiduguri. They accused me of working with Doye. Now, they have charged me with kidnapping, manslaughter and possession of weapon (p. 34).

We see accusations, concocted to silence Amaibi. He is a man of integrity and has never been involved in anything illicit. The government officials are aware that nothing can actually be used to rope him, hence the false accusation. We also see the ill treatment he is subjected to. They are yet to evidence, in court, that he is guilty of the charges; but they have shot him already and have continued to torture him. Amaibi suffers this because he regularly advocates for an end to the devastation of his environment. Garricks' voice or intent is obvious here. Through Amaibi's plight he, Garricks, tries to uncover the episodes of repression which principled individuals suffer in the plundered Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday* is a striking and relatable recreation of the ecological realities of a devastated Niger Delta region of Nigeria. To facilitate an understanding of the investigation, the study's relevant concepts have been conceptualised. The contextualisation has revealed the constituents of the environment, and how they depend on one another for sustenance. The work has also revealed that there are biotic constituents and abiotic constituents, that the biotic constituents affect the abiotic and vice versa. The theory, selected for this investigation of environmental devastation, is ecocriticism; and its tenets indicate that ecocritical analyses are concerned with how the activities of humans affect the environment and how the environment in turn affects humans. Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday* reveals episodes of environmental devastation which characterise the Niger Delta region of Nigeria --- a region known for its oil wealth. In the work, the reader learns about how the activities of Imperial Oil degrade Asiam, the major setting of the work. Activities of the oil company cause water, air, and land pollution as oil spills into the rivers, pollutes them, and kills the fish in them. With the deployment of an ecocritical lens in the analysis of the primary novel, this study has revealed how this devastation of the environment in the work impacts the characters especially negatively. The work has shown how different events, engendered by the devastation of the environment, lead to the deaths of human and nonhuman components of the environment. An arresting part of this study is the interrogation of how the devastated environment influences the decisions of the characters who are angry and hopeless. In addition, the work also reveals how characters, who stand up against the plundering of the environment and the neglect of the people, encounter near-death experiences. Garricks has masterly woven a narrative, with well invented characters and an apt deployment of narrative devices, to decry the devastating effects of environmental degradation on humans and other components of the environment.

REFERENCES

- Achebe, C. (1958). *Things Fall Apart*. London: Heinemann.
- Achebe, C. (1966). *A Man of the People*. London: Heinemann.
- Ajibola, O. & Okoli, B. (2022). Women and Nature for Plunder: An Ecofeminist Study of Chinua Achebe's *A Man of the People*. *UJAH: Unizik Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 23(2), 1-18.
- Anwar, N., Hussain, A., & Amjad, E. (2024). Nature's Voices: Exploring Eco-Feminist Perspectives in Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*. *Annals of Human and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 151-158.
- Barry, P. (2009). *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory*. Waterloo: Manchester University Press.
- Bourque, C. P. A., Cox, R. M., Allen, D. J., Arp, P. A., & Meng, F. R. (2005). Special Extent of Winter Events in Eastern North America. *Global Change Biology*, 11(9), 1477-1492.
- Brown, B. J., Hanson, M. E., Liverman, D. M., & Merideth, R. W. (1987). Global Sustainability: Towards Definition. *Environmental Management*, 11(6), 713--719.
- Buell, L. (1995). *The Environmental Imagination: Thoreau, Nature Writing, and the Formation of American Culture*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Egya, S. E. (2016). Nature and Environmentalism of the Poor: Ecopoetry from the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. *Journal of African Cultural Studies*, 28(1), 1-12.
- Eze, M. O. (2017). Humanitis-Eco(Eco-humanism): An African Environmental Theory. *The Palgrave Handbook of African Publishing* (pp. 621-632).
- Fakemi, A. (2022). Petro-Fiction and Pseudo Environmental Activism: The Defining Moments in Chimeka Garricks' *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*. *Open Access Library Journal*, 9, 1-6.
- Garricks, C. (2010). *Tomorrow Died Yesterday*. Abuja: Paperworth Books Limited.
- Glotfelty, I. C. B. & Fromm, H. (1996). *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology*. G. A.: University of Georgia Press.
- Gogoi, G. (2014). An Ecocritical Approach to Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and *Arrow of God*. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(11), 1-4
- Haeckel, E. (1866). *Generelle Morphologie der Organisme*. Berlin: Georg Reimer.
- Kekeghe, S. E. (2019). "Ecological Favour in Christian Otobotekere's *Around and About 1* and *Beyond Sound and Voice*". In *Between the Crown and the Muse: Poetry and Politics of Christian Otobotekere*. Ed. Ogaga Okuyade. 131-143.
- Kekeghe, S. E. (2021). "Dramatic Art, Medical Ethics and Rehabilitation: Patient-Centered Therapeutic Relationship in Omobowale's *The President's Physician*". In: *International Journal of Literature and Arts*. Special Issue: *Illnesses, Diseases and Medicalisation in African Literature* 9 (4). 1116-2619.
- Merchant, C. (2003). *Reinventing Eden: The fate of nature in Western culture*. Routledge.
- Molles, M. C. (2002). *Ecology: Concepts and Applications*. Boston: McGraw Hill.
- Okoye-Ugwu, S. (2022). A Manifesto for the Fluidity of the Igbo Space and Achebe's Reconstructions in his Narratives. *Sprin Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(05), 250-260.
- Rueckert, W. (1978). Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism. *Iowa Review*, 9(1), 71-86.
- Slaymaker, W. (2001). Ecoing the Other(s): The Call of Global Green and Black African Responses. *PMLA (Publication of the Modern Language Association America)*, 116(1), 129-144).
- White, D. F., Rudy, A. P., & Gareau, B. J. (2016). *Environments, natures and social theory:*